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3 Supporting Information

4 Layered double hydroxides as slow-release fertilizer
5 compounds for the micronutrient molybdenum

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16 **Figure S1** The XRD patterns of the as-synthesized ZnAl LDHs.

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18 **Figure S2** The XRD patterns of the MoO₄-loaded ZnAl LDHs.

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20 **Figure S3** Graphical representation of the expected differences in Al distribution in the basal plane of the three ZnAl LDHs, as
 21 derived from the MoO_4 adsorption and intercalation properties of these LDHs.

22 **Table S1** The final pH of the external incubation solution of the Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al LDHs, reported with standard error (n=2).

	Final pH of external solution
Control	8.06 ± 0.08
Na ₂ Mo ₄ REF	8.19 ± 0.04
Na ₂ MoO ₄	8.14 ± 0.04
MoO ₄ -Zn ₂ Al	8.07 ± 0.03
MoO ₄ -Zn ₃ Al	8.18 ± 0.01
MoO ₄ -Zn ₄ Al	8.10 ± 0.01

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 25 **Figure S4** The anion exchange of MoO₄-loaded Zn₂Al, Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al LDHs incubated in solutions containing varying soil solution
 26 anions, presented on a scale of molar compound exchange, with the anions desorbed in this reaction on the positive axis and the
 27 adsorbed anions on the negative axis. The values above the bars represent the relative MoO₄ desorption from the materials in
 28 the different conditions, while the values below the bars represent the final pH of the respective exchange solution.

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30 **Figure S5** The XRD patterns of the MoO₄-loaded Zn₂Al, Zn₃Al and Zn₄Al LDHs before incubation, and after incubation *i*) in the
 31 presence of soil solution anions Cl, NO₃, SO₄, CO₃ and PO₄ or *ii*) in absence of counter anions.